

Thermal Analysis of Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger by Using Altered Baffles

Dr.J.Bala Bhaskara Rao ¹, V.Jayaram ², V.Saicharan ³, G.SaiSiva ⁴, Ch.Giridhar ⁵

Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering and Technology

Students, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering and Technology

Abstract - The shell and tube heat exchanger is utilized to transfer heat energy between fluids, with tubes enclosed within a shell. It finds applications in various fields like power generation, refrigeration, and waste heat recovery. To minimize pressure drop in the shell side, helical baffles with different pitches replace conventional baffles, facilitating smoother fluid flow and reducing stagnation points. In this study, fluid flow analysis of the heat exchanger was conducted using CATIA and FLUENT software. Ender Ozden's experimental findings on shell side pressure drop with conventional baffles were validated numerically with a negligible 2% error. Further investigation considered helical baffles with pitches ranging from 100mm to 200mm in a turbulent flow regime (5000-20000 range). Water was used as the working fluid for both the shell and tube sides, with copper and stainless steel as tube and shell materials, respectively. The k-ε model was employed for turbulent simulations. Results indicate that a 150mm pitch helical baffle yields the lowest pressure drop in the shell side.

Keywords: Heat exchanger, Baffles, Pressure drop, Fluent, CATIA

I. INTRODUCTION

In a shell-and-tube heat exchanger, fluid flows through the tubes while another fluid circulates within the space between the tubes and the shell. The basic configuration of a horizontal shell-and-tube condenser with various components is illustrated in the figure. One fluid flows on the shell side, where steam passes across between pairs of baffles and then travels parallel to the tubes as it moves from one baffle compartment to another. There are significant variations among shell-and-tube heat exchangers depending on the specific application. Representative tube bundle configurations used in shell-and-tube heat exchangers are depicted in the figure. CFD analysis of the optimized heat exchanger reveals flow patterns and temperature distribution, with experimental validation. Baffles are found to significantly impact shell side flow, leading to exploration of new baffle geometries enhancing thermal performance while reducing pressure drops and operating costs [1]. A mini STE computational model was developed, analyzing baffle cut, spacing, and shell and tube diameter's impact on pressure drop and heat transfer coefficient. Simulation utilized turbulence models like Spalart-Allmaras, k-ε standard, and k-ε realizable, validated against existing literature for accuracy. Results showed a 44% reduction in pressure drop and a 60.66% increase in heat transfer with the modified heat exchanger design [2]. Comparative analysis reveals significant performance advantages of segmental baffle heat exchangers over helical baffle heat exchangers for the same geometrical configurations, suggesting potential for innovation in helix baffle angle optimization [3]. Numerical study on segmented baffle unidirectional shell and tube heat exchanger using k-ε model. Analysis varying baffle number, keeping other parameters constant, for heat transfer rate and shell side pressure drop [4]. Using ANSYS Fluent, CFD simulations were performed, validated against experimental geometry. Results show a 60° baffle angle yielded over 40 kW heat flow, while a horizontal elliptic profile achieved over 29 kW at 0.5 kg•s⁻¹ mass flow rate [5]. Reduced spacing creates higher turbulence, enhancing heat transfer rates. More baffles increase the fluid path, boosting effective heat transfer area and rates [6-7]. It highlights factors influencing performance and compares various baffle orientations, with 40° inclination and low spacing often proving most effective. Sealing strips notably enhance performance, particularly with segmented baffles [8-9]. By varying parameters like inlet velocity, thermal conductivity, baffle spacing, and tube arrangement, effects on heat transfer and outlet temperature reduction were analyzed. Results indicate significant impacts, highlighting the potential for design improvements in shell and tube heat exchangers [10-11]. Theoretical properties of the NANO fluids are calculated and used in a 3D model of the heat exchanger via CREO parametric, followed by CFD

analysis using ANSYS. Detailed geometry and fine mesh ensure model validation against heat transfer formulas, offering Heat Exchanger designers a CFD-based design approach, reducing dependence on physical prototypes and revision needs [12-14]. The novelty of this investigation is on the use of helical baffles with different pitch to diameter ratios to improve thermal efficiency in shell side of shell and tube heat exchanger.

II. METHODOLOGIES

CATIA (Computer Aided Three-dimensional Interactive Application) is a multi-platform CAD/CAM/CAE commercial software suite developed by the French company Assault Systems. Written in the C++ programming language, CATIA is the cornerstone of the Assault Systems product lifecycle management software suite

Different Virtual Models of Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger

III. MESHING & CFD ANALYSIS

Heat transfer is built in the ANSYS workbench design module. It is a counter-flow heat transfer. First, the fluid flow (fluent) module from the workbench is selected. The design modeller opens as a new window as the geometry is double clicked. At first a generally coarser work is produced. This work contains blended cells (Tetra and Hexahedral cells) having both triangular and quadrilateral countenances at the boundaries or limits. Care is taken to utilize organized hexahedral cells however much as could be expected. It is intended to diminish numerical dissemination however much as could be expected by organizing the work in a well way, especially close to the divider locale. Later on, a fine work is produced. For this fine work, the edges and areas of high temperature and pressure slopes are finely coincided.

Meshed models of Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger

The different surfaces of the solid are named as per required inlets and outlets for inner and outer fluids. Save project again at this point and close the window. Refresh and update project on the workbench. Now open the setup. The ANSYS Fluent Launcher will open in a window. Set dimension as 3D, option as Double Precision, processing as Serial type and hit OK. The Fluent window will open.

Materials are create /edit option is clicked to add water-liquid, steel and copper to the list of fluid and solid respectively from the fluent database.

Fluid Properties

Fluids properties	Density (ρ) Kg/m ³	Prandtl number	Thermal conductivity(K) W/m K	Specific heat C_p J/kgK	Dynamic viscosity (μ) Kg/m-s
Water	998.2	159	0.6	4182	0.001003

Material Properties

Material properties	Density (ρ) Kg/m ³	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio
Copper	8978	110	0.34
Stainless steel	8030	207	0.3

Boundary conditions are utilized by the need of the model. The bay and outlet conditions are characterized as speed delta and pressure outlet. As this is a counter-stream with two tubes so there are two gulfs and two outlets. The dividers are independently indicated with particular limit conditions. No slip condition is considered for every divider. But the tube dividers every divider is set to zero health flux condition. The insights about all limit conditions can be found in the table as given beneath. After giving the boundary conditions to the inner and outer fluid, finally we have to run the calculations. The number of iteration is set to 500 and the solution is calculated and various contours, vectors and plots are obtained.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The objective of this project is to evaluate the minimum pressure drop in shell side of Shell and Tube Heat Transfer. When pressure difference is more, it will caused for increasing of entering velocity and discharge. Baffles are the main parameters which influence the pressure drop in shell side of shell and tube heat transfer. These Baffles are optimized by using fluid flow analysis.

Ender Ozden's study focused on analyzing pressure drop in the shell side of a shell and tube heat exchanger, utilizing segmented baffles and CFD analysis. He determined that a baffle cut of 36% minimized pressure drop while maximizing thermal performance. The boundary conditions in Ozden's research included a shell inlet temperature of 300 K, zero gauge pressure at the outlet nozzle for relative pressure drop determination, no-slip conditions on surfaces, zero heat flux at the outer shell wall, and constant wall temperature of 450 K on tube walls. Upon comparison with our research, the deviation in results was found to be less than 2%.

The shell and tube heat transfer with helical baffle of 100,125,150,175 and 200 pitches considered for this analysis at different mass flow rates in turbulent region. In this analysis four mass flow rates are considered and analyzed the shell side pressure drop in between the Reynolds number range 5000 to 20000. Flow line of pressure drop in shell and tube side at the Reynolds number range 5000 to 20000 and 100,125,150,175 and 200 pitches.

Pressure drop values at different Reynolds numbers at 100 mm pitch

Reynolds number	5555	10100	15155	20200
Pressure drop (Pascal)	496.3882	1189.592	2462.091	4232.691

Pressure drop values at different Reynolds numbers at 125 mm pitch

Reynolds number	5555	10100	15155	20200
Pressure drop (Pascal)	433.6109	991.9478	2153.247	3742.742

Pressure drop values at different Reynolds numbers at 150 mm pitch

Reynolds number	5555	10100	15155	20200
Pressure drop (Pascal)	344.5621	966.0106	1941.968	3226.858

Pressure drop values at different Reynolds numbers at 175 mm pitch

Reynolds number	5555	10100	15155	20200
Pressure drop(Pascal)	466.1469	1097.426	2260.187	3831.829

Pressure drop values at different Reynolds numbers at 200 mm pitch

Reynolds number	5555	10100	15155	20200
Pressure drop (Pascal)	489.9781	1057.252	2364.514	3933.056

From the all above cases it is concluded that the pressure drop increases with increases of Reynolds number. At different pitches of helical baffle the analysis are conducted at different Reynolds number and at 150 mm pitch helical baffle gives less pressure drop in shell side of shell and tube heat transfer as shown in the below graph.

V. CONCLUSION

The thermal performance of a shell and tube heat exchanger with 36% baffle cut at 60 degrees tube orientation and round tubes was numerically examined and compared with Ender Ozden's results. The flow is incompressible and turbulent for this investigation. The pressure drop in shell side of shell and tube heat exchanger is evaluated along the length of the heat exchanger. The percentage of error is 2%. CFD investigation were evaluated on Shell and Tube Heat exchanger with various pitch to diameter ratio's of helical baffles and calculated the shell side pressure drop. Here we considered helical baffle with 100mm, 125mm, 150mm, 175mm and 200mm and at different Reynolds numbers the shell side pressure drop was ascertained by utilizing FLUENT. It is reasoned that the pressure drop increments with increments of Reynolds number. At various pitches of helical astound the examination are directed at various Reynolds number and at 150 mm pitch helical baffle gives less pressure drop in shell side of shell and tube heat exchanger.

VI. REFERENCES

1. Ahmet AYDINa, Halit YASARb, Tahsin ENGINb* , and Ekrem BUYUKKAYA , “**OPTIMIZATION AND CFD ANALYSIS OF A SHELL-AND-TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER WITH A MULTI SEGMENTAL BAFFLE**” THERMAL SCIENCE : Year 2022, Vol. 26, No. 1A, pp. 1-12
2. Shuvam Mohanty¹ and Rajesh Arora ,“**CFD ANALYSIS OF A SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER WITH SINGLE SEGMENTAL BAFFLES**”, IJAME, 2020 ,VOL. 17, ISSUE 2, 7890 – 7901
3. Netra Ravindra Lagad¹ Aishwarya Shivachandar² Jyoti Sharad Bodhale³ , “**ANALYTICAL AND CFD ANALYSIS OF SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER WITH SEGMENTAL AND HELICAL BAFFLES**”,IJERT ISSN: 2278-0181 ,ICNTE-2015 , Volume 3, Issue 01 ,PP 1-6
4. Rakesh Kumar Roshan¹ and Vijaykant Pandey. “**COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS ANALYSIS OF SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER WITH DIFFERENT BAFFLES**” IJAEM ,Volume 5, Issue 7 July 2023, pp: 449-460
5. José Estupiñán-Campos ¹ , William Quitiaquez ^{1,2,*} , César Nieto-Londoño ³ and Patricio Quitiaquez ^{2,4} : “**NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE HEAT TRANSFER INSIDE A SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER CONSIDERING DIFFERENT VARIATIONS IN THE GEOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF THE DESIGN**“ Energies 2024, 17, 691 ,pp 1-17
6. Yalla Vara Prasad¹ , J D Venkatesh² “**ANALYSIS OF SHELL-AND-TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER PERFORMANCE USING SEGMENTAL BAFFLES THROUGH COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS (CFD)**” JETIR, Volume 10, Issue 6 , June 2023 , pp 126-133
7. Saurabh Sharma*¹ & Ritesh Kumar Dewangan² “**A REVIEW ON SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER (STHX) USING VARIOUS ORIENTATION ANGLE OF BAFFLE**”, IJESRT, 6(10): October, 2017, pp 366-369.
8. Hamid Bin ZAHIDA, Abdullah MUBASHARa, Muhammad WAQASb, Muhammad Hamid SIDDIQI c , Umair MUNIRa, and Syed Murawat Abbas NAQVIa* “**EXPERIMENTAL AND CFD SIMULATION STUDY OF SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGERS WITH DIFFERENT BAFFLE SEGMENT CONFIGURATIONS** “THERMAL SCIENCE: Year 2023, Vol. 27, No. 1B, pp. 843-853
9. Umer Zahid, Ahmad Hanan, Tariq Feroze & Sohaib Khan,” **ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OPTIMISATION PARAMETERS OF SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER USING CFD**” Australian Journal of Mechanical Engineering, 26 Apr 2021 pp 1-15

10. Yatna Bhagat* **“STUDIES ON SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER ANALYSIS: A REVIEW”** JAMS, vol. 2, no. 2, June 2023, pp. 52-57.
11. Ravi Kumar Gupta¹ , Deenoo Pawar² **“DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER USING DIFFERENT TUBES MATERIALS”** JETIR, Volume 8, Issue 7 ,July 2021 pp -659-667
12. Mukkera Hemanth ¹ , Sandeep Mulabagal ² ,**“ CFD ANALYSIS OF SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER WITH AND WITHOUT BAFFLES BY USING NANO FLUIDS”** JETIR , Volume 4, Issue 12,December 2017, pp 25-31
13. S. Chellappa Lecturer (Senior. Grade),” **HEAT TRANSFER IMPROVEMENT ON THE SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER USING NANO FLUIDS”**IJMET, Volume 13, Issue 10, October 2022, pp. 36-41.
14. Mehmet Turgay Pamuk,” **CFD SIMULATION OF A SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER”** Proceedings of the 6 th World Congress on Mechanical, Chemical, and Material Engineering Prague,Paper No. ICCPE 105, August, 2020 pp 1-8